

To help infectious disease management, particularly during vaccination campaigns, there is a need for accurate differentiation between vaccinated animals and those infected. **DIVA** diagnostic tests are important to reach this distinction. These tests detect specific markers that indicate either vaccination-induced immunity (serological tests) or the presence of a microorganism (molecular tests).

Serological DIVA

The test detects antibodies produced in response to vaccination or infection. Specific antibodies or antibody combinations, so called antibody profiles, are produced for each situation. Antibody profiles can be detected and differentiated by DIVA tests.

Molecular DIVA

These nucleic acid based-assays, are used to investigate the genetic composition of the micro-organism recovered from the animals. This will identify specific strains or sequences, which will allow differentiation between so called wild-type and vaccine strains.

Applications: in surveillance DIVA test are used to monitor the prevalence of both vaccinated and infected animals separately. In Vaccination program monitoring DIVA allows public health agencies to assess the efficacy of vaccination programs by accurately estimating the number of individuals with vaccine-induced immunity.